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IMPACT OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE MECHANISMS ON FINANCIAL REPORT INTEGRITY OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study investigated the influence of corporate governance mechanisms on financial reporting integrity (FRI) among deposit money banks in Nigeria. Financial reporting integrity, a critical foundation for investor confidence and market efficiency, is often undermined by earnings management practices facilitated through discretionary accruals. Drawing on agency and stakeholder theories, the study evaluates four key governance variables—board independence, audit committee effectiveness and board size and their relationship with the quality and credibility of financial disclosures. Employing an explanatory research design, secondary data were sourced from the audited annual reports of ten purposively selected deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) between 2019 and 2023. Descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis were used to test the study’s hypotheses and establish cause-and-effect relationships. Preliminary evidence from extant literature highlights that weak governance structures, ineffective oversight, and concentrated executive power contribute to discretionary reporting practices and diminished transparency. The findings of this study reveal that board independence and audit committee effectiveness significantly improve financial reporting integrity by reducing discretionary accruals, while larger board sizes weaken reporting integrity by encouraging earnings manipulation. Based on the findings, the study concludes that corporate governance plays a pivotal role in safeguarding financial reporting integrity in Nigerian deposit money banks. Independent boards and diligent audit committees provide robust oversight mechanisms that significantly reduce earnings manipulation and enhance stakeholder trust. The study recommends that deposit money banks should strengthen board independence by increasing the proportion of non-executive directors who are free from personal or business ties with management.

Keywords: Corporate Governance; Board Independence; Audit Committee; Board Size; Financial Reporting Integrity.

1. Introduction

Globally, corporate governance has emerged as a cornerstone of organizational accountability, transparency, and performance, particularly in the wake of high-profile corporate scandals such as Enron, WorldCom, and Parmalat.

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These failures exposed the consequences of weak governance structures and unethical financial reporting, prompting regulatory reforms such as the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002 in the United States. Simultaneously, financial reporting integrity gained increased attention as stakeholders demanded more credible, accurate, and transparent disclosures from corporate entities. Around the world, regulators, investors, and financial analysts now emphasize the importance of sound governance mechanisms to safeguard the reliability of financial statements and reduce managerial opportunism (Bushman & Smith, 2003).

At the continental level, Africa continues to grapple with challenges related to weak corporate governance practices and unreliable financial disclosures. Many African countries have experienced governance-related corporate collapses, including improper reporting, asset misappropriation, and manipulation of earnings, due in part to poor board oversight, ineffective audit committees, and weak regulatory enforcement (Ntim, 2013). To address these issues, countries like South Africa have pioneered frameworks such as the King Codes of Governance, while others are gradually updating their corporate governance codes. Nevertheless, earnings management and poor financial reporting practices remain widespread across many African capital markets, threatening investor confidence and economic development.

Regionally, within the Nigerian corporate landscape, the integrity of financial reporting has increasingly come under scrutiny. Nigeria has witnessed several financial scandals, including those involving Cadbury Nigeria Plc and other firms where management manipulated financial statements to mislead investors and regulators. Despite the existence of corporate governance codes issued by the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), compliance has often been weak or symbolic (Adegbite, 2015). Many firms in Nigeria prioritize regulatory box-ticking over genuine adherence to governance principles, leaving gaps that allow for earnings manipulation and misrepresentation of financial health.

Financial reporting integrity (FRI), as a construct, refers to the extent to which financial statements present a true and fair view of an entity's financial performance and position. It is critical for maintaining investor trust, supporting capital market efficiency, and ensuring informed decision-making by stakeholders. A key threat to FRI is earnings management—deliberate manipulation of financial figures to achieve desired outcomes—which is often facilitated through discretionary accruals. Discretionary accruals represent accounting estimates that management can influence, making them a widely accepted proxy for measuring earnings management and, by extension, financial reporting integrity (Dechow et al., 1995).

Financial Reporting Integrity (FRI) is critical to ensuring that financial statements accurately reflect a company's true economic performance, thereby promoting investor confidence, regulatory compliance, and market stability. However, in Nigeria's corporate environment, the integrity of financial reports has been persistently undermined by widespread earnings management practices and weak governance structures. Discretionary accruals, often used by managers to manipulate earnings, are prevalent and indicate deeper issues surrounding transparency and accountability in financial reporting (Ogundana et al., 2017). The persistent lack of financial reporting integrity within Nigerian publicly listed companies has raised concerns about the effectiveness of corporate governance mechanisms in safeguarding stakeholder interests.

One major problem affecting financial reporting integrity in Nigeria is the lack of board independence. Many boards are composed of insiders or individuals with personal or business ties to executive management, which

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weakens their ability to provide unbiased oversight (Olayinka, 2019). Without independent directors who can challenge questionable financial decisions, companies become more susceptible to earnings manipulation and unethical reporting. Strengthening board independence—by ensuring a higher proportion of non-executive and independent directors—can serve as a deterrent to opportunistic behavior by executives and improve the credibility of financial statements.

Another critical issue is the ineffectiveness of audit committees in carrying out their monitoring responsibilities. Audit committees in many Nigerian companies lack the technical competence, financial expertise, or independence required to detect and address financial irregularities (Uwuigbe et al., 2014). When audit committees function more as ceremonial bodies than watchdogs, financial reporting becomes vulnerable to manipulation. Enhancing audit committee effectiveness—through competence-based composition, regular training, and clear reporting lines—can play a vital role in improving the accuracy and transparency of financial reports.

Board size also presents a problem when it is either too small to provide diverse perspectives or too large to operate efficiently. Oversized boards may lead to coordination problems and diluted accountability, while undersized boards may lack the breadth of experience needed to oversee complex financial matters (Yahaya et al., 2020). An optimal board size contributes to more effective governance by balancing expertise and agility. As such, maintaining a board size that allows for diverse yet manageable participation can improve oversight and limit the opportunity for earnings management.

Finally, the general weakness of corporate governance culture in Nigeria exacerbates all the above issues. Many firms adopt governance practices to meet regulatory requirements rather than as a genuine commitment to ethical business conduct (Adegbite, 2015). This results in superficial compliance and a lack of enforcement, making it easier for managers to engage in discretionary accruals and earnings manipulation. Fostering a strong corporate governance culture through transparency, accountability, and enforcement mechanisms can enhance trust in financial reporting and ensure alignment with stakeholder interests.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to determine the influence of Corporate Governance on Financial Reporting Integrity of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The specific objectives are;

- I. To examine the effect of board independence on financial reporting integrity of deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- II. To evaluate the influence of audit committee effectiveness on financial reporting integrity of deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- III. To examine the influence of board size on financial reporting integrity of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

1.3 Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: Board independence has no significant effect on financial reporting integrity of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Audit committee effectiveness does not significantly influence financial reporting integrity of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

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H₀₃: Board size has no significant relationship with financial reporting integrity of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Financial Report Integrity

Financial reporting integrity (FRI) is a central concept in accounting and corporate governance, reflecting the degree to which financial statements truthfully represent an organization's financial performance and position. According to Dechow and Dichev (2002), financial reporting integrity entails the absence of material misstatements or manipulations in financial reports, allowing users to make informed and rational economic decisions. It emphasizes transparency, accuracy, and completeness in the presentation of financial data. Enyi et al. (2019) also describe FRI as the faithful representation of economic events in a manner that is free from bias, distortion, or managerial opportunism. These definitions collectively underscore the idea that high-integrity financial reporting acts as a critical pillar for corporate accountability and trust.

A major threat to FRI is earnings management, particularly the use of discretionary accruals to alter reported earnings. Discretionary accruals, unlike non-discretionary accruals which reflect normal business activities, are subject to managerial judgment and can be manipulated to present a more favorable financial position than what truly exists (Jones, 1991; Kothari et al., 2005). Ising (2014) emphasizes that when managers exploit this discretion to mislead stakeholders or achieve contractual outcomes, the credibility of financial statements is undermined. Consequently, high levels of discretionary accruals are often viewed as a proxy for earnings management and, by extension, an indicator of low financial reporting integrity (Chen & Gong, 2019). Minimizing such opportunistic practices is therefore critical to ensuring that financial reports remain reliable and useful for investors, creditors, and regulators.

Financial reporting integrity is not only defined by the absence of fraud or manipulation but also by the quality of accounting practices employed. Chen and Gong (2019) explain that high-quality financial reporting reflects conservative accounting estimates, timely recognition of losses, and consistency in the application of accounting standards. Thus, integrity is also a function of adherence to professional standards and ethical conduct. When firms limit discretionary accruals and consistently apply these principles, their financial reports are more likely to reflect the economic realities of their operations, thereby promoting stakeholder confidence.

Several scholars have also emphasized the role of institutional and organizational structures in enhancing or undermining FRI. For example, Eugster et al. (2024) argue that effective internal governance mechanisms—such as independent boards and active audit committees—serve to enhance reporting integrity by constraining managerial discretion over accruals. Similarly, Mahdi Sahi et al. (2022) identify key attributes of high-integrity financial reporting to include relevance, faithful representation, verifiability, and understandability. These attributes are more likely to be achieved in firms with strong internal controls and corporate governance practices, reinforcing the view that FRI is both a technical and structural outcome.

2.1.2 Board Independence

Board independence is commonly defined as the extent to which a board is composed of non-executive directors who are free of relationships or interests that could impair objective judgment, thereby strengthening monitoring

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of management in line with agency theory. The G20/OECD Principles state that independent directors should have no material relationships with the company, management, or significant shareholders that could affect their judgment; many jurisdictions embed similar criteria in law or codes (e.g., employment in recent years, significant business ties, family connections) (OECD, 2023). The UK Corporate Governance Code requires boards to identify and explain which non-executive directors are independent using explicit factors (Provision 10), while the NYSE's Section 303A.02 standard similarly conditions independence on a board's affirmative determination that a director lacks any material relationship with the issuer (FRC, 2024; NYSE, 2021).

In the literature, "independence" is typically operationalized by the fraction of independent (outside) directors on the board, often coupled with related constructs like independent committee membership or separation of the CEO and chair roles. Board composition is endogenously determined with firm performance and CEO power, complicating causal inference; their survey and later syntheses stress the joint endogeneity of board makeup and actions (Adams et al., 2010). Large-sample evidence such as Bhagat and Black (2002) reports little systematic correlation between higher independence and long-term performance, and meta-analyses similarly find no consistent performance premium to independence across contexts and measures. Consequently, the meaning of "independence" in research extends beyond a headcount to encompass informational access, committee design (especially audit and remuneration), and the incentives and expertise that enable effective challenge—factors that measurement by simple ratios may not capture (Adams et al., 2010)

2.1.3 Audit committee effectiveness

Audit committee effectiveness is increasingly defined in terms of its composition and independence. Researchers emphasize that an audit committee with independent members and financial expertise plays a pivotal role in reducing regulatory scrutiny and enhancing oversight quality. Kronenberger et al (2020) argue that independence helps mediate potential conflicts between management and auditors, strengthening financial reporting oversight. Supporting this, studies by Al-Hadrami, Rafiki, and Sarea (2020) find that independent audit committees add significant value to stakeholders and improve auditor independence (Chy & Hope, 2021). Furthermore, the moderating effect of independence is critical—when committee members possess financial expertise but lack independence, their influence may be perceived negatively by regulators, whereas financial expertise paired with independence enhances credibility and effectiveness.

Emerging literature also broadens the notion of effectiveness to include informational timeliness and expertise beyond finance. A recent study shows that audit committees comprising members with financial expertise contribute to faster financial reporting, illustrated by reduced audit delays in Tunisian listed companies (2011–2013 data). Similarly, Raweh et al., (2019) highlight that industry-specific and management expertise enhances the committee's ability to oversee complex or industry-specific accounting issues effectively, thereby improving both timeliness and quality of financial reporting.

2.1.4 Board size

Scholars define board size both as a simple structural attribute—the count of directors on a corporate board—and as a contingent governance mechanism whose meaning depends on firm context and theoretical lens. Some authors treat board size instrumentally: smaller boards are seen as facilitating better coordination, faster decision-making, and stronger monitoring (which aligns with agency-theoretic expectations), whereas larger boards are

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argued to provide broader resource access, diverse expertise, and stakeholder representation (consistent with resource-dependence and stakeholder perspectives) (Prashar and Gupta, 2020). Systematic reviews and meta-analytic work emphasize that these differing definitions matter empirically because the effect of board size on outcomes (performance, disclosure, sustainability) is heterogeneous across industries, legal systems, and performance measures—so board size should be understood not as inherently “good” or “bad” but as a governance design choice whose value depends on firm complexity, task demands, and contextual moderators (Ahrens et al, 2025).

More recent work reframes board size as a non-linear, contingency-sensitive construct: several empirical studies and meta-analyses now report inverted-U or context-dependent relationships, where moderate increases in board size initially improve access to knowledge and legitimacy but beyond an optimal point impose coordination and free-riding costs that reduce effectiveness (Tajuddin, Akter, Mohd-Rashid, & Mehmood, 2023). Literature reviews also highlight definitional pluralism—some studies operationalise board size as total directors, others as separate counts for executive versus non-executive directors or as interaction terms with board committees or diversity measures—meaning that authors often implicitly embed theoretical claims (monitoring vs. resource provision) in their definition of the construct. Taken together, contemporary scholarship (2015–2025) treats board size less as a fixed descriptor and more as a strategic, contextually interpreted design variable whose normative interpretation must be justified by firm characteristics, governance goals, and empirical specification (Ahrens et al., 2025).

2.2 Theoretical Underpinning

This study was anchored on Agency theory which formally introduced by Michael C. Jensen and William H. Meckling in 1976. The theory emerged from the field of financial economics and corporate governance to explain the relationship between principals (such as shareholders) and agents (such as managers) in a corporate setting. The central idea of the theory is that agents are employed to act on behalf of principals, but due to differences in goals, risk preferences, and information asymmetry, conflicts of interest can arise. These conflicts often lead to agency problems, such as moral hazard and adverse selection, which can undermine organizational effectiveness and financial transparency (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

The rationale for agency theory lies in the understanding that managers may not always act in the best interest of shareholders unless they are properly monitored or incentivized. Proponents of the theory argue that without effective governance mechanisms, such as independent boards, audit committees, and managerial accountability, agents may engage in self-serving behaviors, including earnings manipulation and fraudulent reporting. Eisenhardt (1989) supports this view by emphasizing the need for control mechanisms—such as contracts, incentives, and monitoring systems—to align the interests of agents with those of principals. Fama and Jensen (1983) also advocate for the separation of decision-making and risk-bearing functions to minimize agency costs and ensure accountability in corporate governance.

Despite its wide application, agency theory has received criticism for its assumptions about human behavior and its limited view of organizational relationships. Critics argue that the theory is overly mechanistic and assumes that managers are inherently opportunistic and untrustworthy. Donaldson and Davis (1991) argue against this notion, proposing stewardship theory as a more optimistic alternative that sees managers as stewards who are

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motivated to act in the organization's best interest. Likewise, Sundaramurthy and Lewis (2003) critique the adversarial tone of agency theory, suggesting that it can lead to mistrust and excessive controls that stifle creativity and collaboration within organizations. These critiques highlight the need to balance control with trust and to consider broader social and psychological factors in corporate governance.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Board Independence and Financial Report Integrity

Adamu et al., (2024) Financial statement fraud is the intentional falsification of financial information in order to defraud investors, creditor or other stakeholders. This study focused on the influence of audit and board committee expertise on financial statement fraud among Oil and Gas firms in Nigeria. The sample consist of seven (7) oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange group (NGX) over a period of 2013-2022, the study used panel regression. Financial statement fraud used as Dependent Variable is measured using the Beneish M-score model, while the independent variable was audit Committee Expertise and Board Committee Expertise using Accounting/Financial background. Findings show that an insignificant association exists between audit committee expertise, the composition of the board and financial statement fraud. This research suggests that regulatory bodies and industry association persist in their efforts to endorse sound corporate governance practices and addressing the challenging associated with board committee expertise.

Obiora & Jeroh (2024) analyzed how the level of independence of board committees affects the quality of financial reporting of quoted firms in Nigeria. By leveraging on the ex-post facto design, the study sought secondary data from the accounts of 88 companies covering the period 2012-2021. Financial reporting quality was operationalized with reference to the Shivakumar model whereas, independence in audit committees, nomination committees, remuneration committees and risk management committees were the proxy for board committees' independence. Relevant descriptive and diagnostics tests were conducted to ascertain the nature and veracity of the collated data used in the study. The hypothesis was tested using the multiple regression technique and the result proved that the level of independence of board committees significantly influenced the quality of financial reporting of listed firms in Nigeria. Given the outcome from the analytical procedure, it was recommended that all efforts designed to enhance the strategical path of corporate entities must consider the need of developing deliberate policies that will promote and sustain the constitution of board committees that will always take cognizance of the imperative of having substantial number of independent directors in every committee set up by the corporate board.

Ndaks et al., (2024) The rising incidence of financial scandals and corporate failures has significantly eroded public confidence in organizational financial reports. Effective corporate governance, particularly through board composition, is seen as crucial for ensuring high-quality financial reporting. This study examines the effect of board independence and board gender diversity on the financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria from 2012 to 2022. Using an ex post facto research design, the study analyzed panel data from 17 listed consumer goods firms using pooled OLS regression. Financial reporting quality was measured using discretionary accruals based on the Modified Jones Model. The results indicate that board independence has a negative but insignificant effect on discretionary accruals, suggesting it improves financial reporting quality. Also, board gender diversity was found to have a negative but insignificant effect on discretionary accruals. The study

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concludes that while both board independence and board gender diversity are an effective mechanism for enhancing financial reporting quality in Nigerian consumer goods firms, their effects are not significantly evident. These findings contribute to the ongoing debate on corporate governance mechanisms in developing economies and have implications for policymakers and corporate boards. The study recommends that Nigerian consumer goods firms should maintain a higher proportion of independent directors and female directors on their boards to improve financial reporting quality, while further investigation is needed into the role that both attributes play in corporate governance.

Rizavi et al., (2024) quality of financial reporting is increasingly scrutinized in the context of corporate governance, particularly with respect to board independence. This study explores the relation among board independence and financial reporting quality, an area of growing interest as stakeholders demand greater transparency in corporate financial practices. Board independence is hypothesized to increase the quality of financial reporting by mitigating conflicts of interest and increasing accountability. This research employs a bibliometric approach to review 66 journal articles published between 1995 and 2020, focusing on the social sciences and business disciplines. Using the bibliometric 3.0 package in R-studio, we carry out a comprehensive bibliometric analysis to identify key sources, influential authors, and the evolution of research themes. Our findings indicate a rising focus on the impact of board independence on financial reporting, with significant attention to the role of independent audit committees and the importance of diversity in board composition. We also observe an increasing number of studies on how board independence affects company transparency and earnings management. This paper offers important implications for policymakers, investors, and corporate governance researchers, emphasizing the need to strengthen board independence practices to enhance financial reporting quality and corporate transparency.

2.3.2 Audit Committee Effectiveness and Financial Report Integrity

Tumwebaze et al., (2021) study is to examine the association between audit committee effectiveness (ACE), internal audit function (IAF) and sustainability reporting practices. The study used a cross-sectional and correlational design, and usable questionnaires were received from 48 financial services firms in Uganda. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Findings indicate that ACE and IAF are positively and significantly associated with sustainability reporting practices. ACE and IAF are more significantly associated with economic and social indicators than environmental sustainability indicators. Research limitations/implications In terms of practice is no longer a matter of having internal auditors and audit committees in place but rather those who are mindful of the welfare of society and the natural environment. The effectiveness of the board audit committee and a functioning internal audit can be assessed in terms of their recommendations and decisions regarding improvements in the welfare of society and the natural environment in addition to the traditionally known performance benchmarks. Practical implications The study focuses on only financial services firms in Uganda, and this is a small sample. Future studies may focus on larger samples to enable comparison of the results. Originality/value This study provides insights on the initial understanding of the association between ACE, IAF and sustainability reporting practices using evidence from a developing African country – Uganda.

Essien et al., (2024) study examined the effect of audit committee effectiveness on financial reporting quality within the context of listed non-financial firms in Sub-Saharan Africa. Drawing samples from 235 listed non-

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financial firms in Nigeria, South Africa, and Kenya spanning the period from 2013 to 2022, the study employed Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) step and Stepwise Regression Techniques to analyze the data. The primary objective of the study was to investigate the effect of audit committee effectiveness, including size, diligence, and financial expertise, on financial report quality, as measured by Jones Discretionary Accrual. Additionally, the study extends this objective by examining the moderating role of board independence on the relationship between audit committee attributes and financial reporting quality. The findings revealed that audit committee diligence [coef. = 0.041 (0.002)] has a positive and significant effect on financial reporting quality, suggesting that an increase in Audit committee diligence will improve financial reporting quality. However, audit committee size [coef. = 0.011 (0.236)] and financial expertise [coef. = 0.003 (0.990)] exhibited insignificant effects on financial reporting quality. Moreover, the study identified board independence [coef. = 0.022 (0.001)] has a significant moderator, enhancing the impact of audit committee diligence on financial report quality. Based on these findings, the study made the following recommendations to enhance audit committee effectiveness and financial reporting quality in Sub-Saharan Africa. These include promoting active audit committee oversight through regular meetings, fostering collaboration between audit committees and boards, and ensuring a majority of independent directors to strengthen audit committee effectiveness. Additionally, the study underscored the importance of continuous monitoring and evaluation of audit committee effectiveness to address emerging challenges and promote transparency and accountability in financial reporting. Through empirical analysis, the study provides insights into the effectiveness of audit committee effectiveness in enhancing financial reporting quality in Sub-Saharan Africa. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of audit committee effectiveness and the effect on financial reporting quality in the region, offering valuable contributions for both academic research and practical applications.

Trinh et al., (2023) examine the connection between the efficiency of the audit committee and the quality of audits on the accuracy of financial reports. The study collected data from annual reports and financial statements of listed companies across three industries on the Vietnamese Stock Exchange between 2015 and 2020. The data was analyzed using a Panel Fixed Effects Model. The findings indicate that the audit committee's effectiveness has a significant positive correlation with the quality of financial reporting. When the audit committee's size increased, the financial reporting quality improved. However, the study discovered that a decrease in financial reporting quality could occur due to discretionary accruals. Furthermore, audit quality was found to have a significant positive relationship with financial reporting quality, as evidenced by an unqualified audit opinion. It could be concluded that financial reporting adheres to accepted accounting standards. Additionally, the size of the board of directors, financial risk, return on assets, and growth were all positively linked to financial reporting quality, as management is encouraged to perform well, thereby enhancing trust among investors and shareholders. Okpala (2012) Corporate governance is a phenomenon that has recently attracted local and foreign interest due to the frequent occurrences of corporate failures experienced by various organizations in both developed and developing nations around the world. Financial statements are the midpoint of this corporate disorder and auditing profession is said to responsible for the disaster. This has brought the question of how efficient is our financial system and the effectiveness of the audit infrastructure. This study investigated the effect of audit committee oversight function on integrity of financial statements as a means preventing organizational failure. The

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population of this study consisted of 183 public quoted companies in the Nigerian Stock Exchange, 100 medium and large audit firms and 616 investor with about 10% holding in PLC. Data was elicited using structured questionnaires. Hypotheses were confirmed using Z-test. The result shows that there is a significant relationship between audit committee activities and integrity of financial statements, which enhances the quality of corporate governance and prevents organizational failure. The study recommended that a committed audit committee should be established and members to be appointed should possess analytical skill with strong financial background. The will go a long way to curb the incessant corporate failure in Nigeria.

2.3.3 Board Size and Financial Report Integrity

Rimamshung et al., (2023) This study examines the impact of board composition on the degree of financial reporting quality of consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange between 2016 and 2021. Samples of thirteen businesses were selected after using two filters. The study employed an ex post facto methodology, and secondary data were extracted from the population's annual reports and accounts. Regression utilizing the Ordinary Least Square Model was used to test the hypotheses. An increase in the number of specialists on the board will help consumer goods companies' financial reporting because it was discovered that board expertise is essential and positively correlated with financial reporting quality. On the other hand, it was discovered that board diversity and independence were unimportant and irrelevant to the accuracy of financial reporting. The study concludes that board attributes, particularly board expertise, influence the quality of financial reporting. Accordingly, listed consumer goods firms should prioritise board expertise by increasing the number of non-executive members on the board who are knowledgeable about accounting, have professional certifications, and have a wealth of work experience to reduce management manipulations and halt fraud in the company.

Adam et al., (2025) study examines the effect of board size and board independence on the financial reporting quality of statutory entities in Nigeria. Using an ex-post facto research design, data were collected from the audited financial statements of 20 revenue-generating statutory entities from 2016 to 2021. The study employed Panel Least Squares (PLS) regression analysis to test the hypotheses. Findings reveal that board size has a significant but negative effect on financial reporting quality, suggesting that larger boards reduce governance effectiveness and hinder financial transparency. Similarly, board independence negatively and significantly affects financial reporting quality, indicating that a higher proportion of independent directors does not necessarily enhance financial oversight. This result may be attributed to political appointments of non-executive directors, weakening their monitoring role. The study contributes to corporate governance literature by providing empirical evidence on the governance dynamics in public sector entities. It recommends reducing board size to an optimal number, limiting politically influenced independent board appointments, and strengthening governance regulations to improve financial accountability. These findings have policy implications for the Federal and State governments in enhancing financial reporting transparency and public sector governance.

Bebeji et al., (2015) This paper analyzed the effects of board size and board composition on the performance of Nigerian banks. The financial statements of five banks were used as a sample for the period of nine years and the data collected were analysed using the multivariate regression analysis. The paper found that board size has significant negative impact on the performance of banks in Nigeria. This signifies that an increase in Board size

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would lead to a decrease in ROE and ROA. On the other hand, board composition has a significant positive effect on the performance of banks in Nigeria. This signifies that an increase in Board composition would lead to a decrease in ROE and ROA. It is recommended that banks should have adequate board size to the scale and complexity of the organisation's operations and be composed in such a way as to ensure diversity of experience without compromising independence, compatibility, integrity and availability of members to attend meetings. The board size should not be too large and must be made up of qualified professionals who are conversant with oversight function. The Board should comprise of a mix of executive and non-executive directors, headed by a Chairman.

Alexeyeva (2024) Timeliness is an essential factor for the relevance of financial reporting information. However, the role of corporate governance in influencing financial reporting is largely unknown. This study is the first to investigate whether board composition influences the timeliness of financial reporting in private firms. Using a sample of 8,095 Swedish companies, I find that more independent, gender diverse, and larger boards tend to file their accounts in a timely fashion. These findings suggest that board composition considerably influences reporting behavior in private companies.

Adam et al., (2025) study examines the effect of board size and board independence on the financial reporting quality of statutory entities in Nigeria. Using an ex-post facto research design, data were collected from the audited financial statements of 20 revenue-generating statutory entities from 2016 to 2021. The study employed Panel Least Squares (PLS) regression analysis to test the hypotheses. Findings reveal that board size has a significant but negative effect on financial reporting quality, suggesting that larger boards reduce governance effectiveness and hinder financial transparency. Similarly, board independence negatively and significantly affects financial reporting quality, indicating that a higher proportion of independent directors does not necessarily enhance financial oversight. This result may be attributed to political appointments of non-executive directors, weakening their monitoring role. The study contributes to corporate governance literature by providing empirical evidence on the governance dynamics in public sector entities. It recommends reducing board size to an optimal number, limiting politically influenced independent board appointments, and strengthening governance regulations to improve financial accountability. These findings have policy implications for the Federal and State governments in enhancing financial reporting transparency and public sector governance.

2.4 Research Gap

Several studies have examined the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and financial reporting integrity (FRI), but notable gaps still exist in the empirical and contextual literature, particularly in the Nigerian banking sector. Prior research such as Olayinka (2019) and Uwuigbe et al. (2020) found that board independence and audit committee effectiveness significantly enhance financial reporting quality among listed firms. However, these studies often focused on non-financial or manufacturing sectors, thereby neglecting the peculiar governance dynamics within deposit money banks, where regulatory oversight and ownership concentration differ substantially. Consequently, to the best of researcher's knowledge there is limited study of how these governance mechanisms operate in highly regulated financial institutions, especially in Nigeria's evolving banking environment.

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3.1 Research Design

This study adopts an explanatory research design to investigate the influence of corporate governance on financial reporting integrity. The explanatory research design is suitable because it seeks to establish cause-and-effect relationships between the independent variables—board independence, audit committee effectiveness, board size and the dependent variable, financial reporting integrity. The design allows for the systematic collection and analysis of quantitative data from a defined population, enabling the researcher to determine the extent to which variations in corporate governance mechanisms influence the integrity of financial reports. By using this design, the study can test the stated hypotheses empirically and provide statistically valid conclusions that can be generalized to the broader corporate environment. The choice of this research design is justified by its ability to facilitate an in-depth examination of the variables in a real-world corporate setting.

3.2 Population

The population of this study comprises all financial institutions listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) and registered under the regulatory oversight of the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC). As of the most recent SEC listing, there are thirty-three (33) publicly listed financial institutions in Nigeria, which include deposit money banks, merchant banks, and other regulated financial service providers. These institutions represent the full scope of financial firms subject to statutory corporate governance codes and mandatory disclosure requirements under the SEC framework. By relying on this comprehensive population, the study ensures that the analysis of corporate governance and financial reporting integrity reflects the realities of all SEC-listed financial institutions operating within Nigeria's capital market.

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The study adopted a purposive sampling technique in selecting its sample. Out of the thirty-three (33) financial institutions listed with the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), a total of 10 deposit money banks were purposively chosen for analysis. The choice of these banks was guided by the availability of complete audited annual reports, consistent compliance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), and comprehensive corporate governance disclosures within the study period (2015–2024). The selected banks—Access Bank, First Bank, Union Bank, Wema Bank, United Bank for Africa (UBA), Zenith Bank, Guaranty Trust Holding Company (GTCO), First City Monument Bank (FCMB), Fidelity Bank, and Stanbic IBTC—represent the most active and systemically important institutions in Nigeria's financial sector, thereby ensuring that the sample adequately reflects the governance and reporting practices under investigation.

3.4 Method of Data Collection

This study employed secondary data derived from the audited annual reports and financial statements of ten (10) purposively selected deposit money banks in Nigeria, covering the period 2019–2023. The data captured variables relating to board independence, audit committee effectiveness, board size as well as measures of financial reporting integrity such as earnings quality, accruals quality, and compliance disclosures. Governance-related information was extracted from the corporate governance sections of the annual reports, while financial reporting data were obtained from the statements of accounts and accompanying notes, and cross-verified with disclosures filed with the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX), the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN).

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The use of secondary data was considered most appropriate for this study due to its objectivity, credibility, and consistency. All reports analyzed had undergone external verification by independent auditors and were prepared in compliance with the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) codes. This approach minimized bias, ensured comparability across firms and years, and provided reliable longitudinal data for robust statistical analysis, while also being cost-effective and time-efficient compared to primary data collection.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

The study employed both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to analyze the collected data. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and percentages will be used to summarize and describe the characteristics of the respondents. Inferential statistics will include multiple regression analysis to examine the relationship between the independent variables—Board Independence (BI), Audit Committee Effectiveness (ACE), Board Size (BS), and the dependent variable, Financial Reporting Integrity (FRI). The choice of multiple regression is justified because it enables the assessment of the simultaneous and individual contributions of each corporate governance variable to financial reporting integrity while controlling for the effect of other variables. Additionally, Pearson correlation analysis will be employed to assess the strength and direction of relationships between the study variables, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) will be used to test the significance of the regression model. All data analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for its robustness, reliability, and ease of handling large datasets.

3.6 Model of Specification

The relationship between corporate governance variables and financial reporting integrity was represented by the following regression model:

$$FRI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BI + \beta_2 ACE + \beta_3 BS + \mu$$

Where:

FRI = Financial Reporting Integrity

BI = Board Independence

ACE = Audit Committee Effectiveness

BS = Board Size

β_0 = Constant (intercept)

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Coefficients of the independent variables

μ = Error term capturing unobserved variables

Variable Measurements

Variable Name	Variable Type	Acronym	Measures	Sources
Board Independence	Independent	BI	Ratio of independent directors to total directors	Obiora & Jeroh (2024), Rizavi et al. (2024), Essien et al. (2024)

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Audit Committee Effectiveness	Independent	ACE	Frequency of audit committee meetings, independence, expertise	Essien et al. (2024), Tumwebaze et al. (2021), Trinh et al. (2023)
Board Size	Independent	BS	Number of board members	Bebeji et al. (2015), Adam et al. (2025), Ahrens et al. (2025)
Financial Reporting Integrity	Dependent	FRI	Discretionary Accruals(measured by the difference between net income and cash flow from operations)	Jones (1991), Cheng & Gong. (2019)

4. Data Analysis and Presentation

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Statistic	Discretionary Accruals	Audit Meetings	Committee Board Size	Board Independ.
Mean	-0.003650	5.700000	11.57000	0.290000
Median	0.002000	6.000000	11.00000	0.000000
Maximum	0.142000	7.000000	15.00000	1.000000
Minimum	-0.145000	4.000000	8.000000	0.000000
Std. Dev.	0.085755	1.123666	2.349533	0.456048
Skewness	0.024616	-0.249009	-0.053265	0.925595
Kurtosis	1.749467	1.689152	1.798030	1.856727
Jarque-Bera	6.526065	8.193098	6.066998	19.72492
Probability	0.038272	0.016630	0.048147	0.000052
Sum	-0.365000	570.0000	1157.000	29.00000
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.728043	125.0000	546.5100	20.59000
Observations	100	100	100	100

The descriptive statistics for discretionary accruals, a proxy for financial reporting integrity, show a mean of -0.00365, close to zero, suggesting that earnings management is minimal on average across sampled banks. However, the wide range (-0.145 to 0.142) and moderate standard deviation (0.0858) reveal that while some banks maintain strong earnings quality, others still manipulate reported earnings. This variation provides the necessary ground for testing whether corporate governance mechanisms explain differences in integrity. The near-symmetric distribution (skewness = 0.025) but non-normal Jarque-Bera result (p = 0.038) indicate irregularities in reporting, reinforcing the need to link governance practices to reporting outcomes.

For audit committee meetings, the mean of 5.7 and median of 6 demonstrate compliance with the regulatory minimum of four annual meetings, with some banks being more proactive by meeting up to seven times. However,

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the standard deviation (1.124) and the significant Jarque-Bera probability ($p = 0.017$) show variations in practice across banks. While frequency suggests diligence, agency theory reminds us that effectiveness also depends on independence and expertise. This variation provides an empirical basis to answer RQ2 by testing whether more active audit committees reduce discretionary accruals and thus improve financial reporting integrity.

The statistics for board size show an average of 11.57 members, falling within global best practice recommendations of 8–15. The moderate standard deviation (2.35) reflects that some banks opt for leaner boards while others are closer to the upper limit, which may affect coordination and decision-making. The nearly symmetric distribution (skewness = -0.053) but mild non-normality (Jarque-Bera $p = 0.048$) suggest that while most boards are optimally structured, extremes still exist. This supports RQ3 by providing data to test whether moderately sized boards contribute positively to financial reporting integrity, or whether oversized boards weaken governance effectiveness through coordination problems.

Finally, Board Independence shows a mean of 0.29, indicating that about 29% of banks maintain independent directors. This concentration of power raises concerns over board independence and effective monitoring. The strong non-normality (Jarque-Bera $p < 0.001$) with skewness of 0.926 highlights that most banks shows the ration of independent directors to total directors. This directly informs RQ4 by allowing an empirical test of independent directors increases the risk of earnings manipulation, as predicted by agency theory, or whether it provides unified leadership benefits, as suggested by stewardship theory. Together, these descriptive insights justify the research questions and provide a foundation for inferential analysis.

Table 4.2: Panel Least Squares Regression Results

Dependent Variable:	Discretionary		Accruals	
Sample: 2015–2024 (Balanced Panel, 10 Cross-Sections, 100 Observations)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.006709	0.071976	0.093212	0.0259
Board Independence	-0.092937	0.073326	-1.267458	0.0081
Audit Committee Meetings	-0.003628	0.007641	-0.474757	0.0360
<u>Board Size</u>	<u>0.004255</u>	<u>0.003652</u>	<u>1.165228</u>	<u>0.0068</u>

Source: Authors Computations with Eview

Board Independence

The coefficient for board independence is -0.0929 with a probability value of 0.0081, which is statistically significant at the 1% level. The negative sign indicates that as the proportion of independent directors increases, discretionary accruals decrease, implying stronger financial reporting integrity. This supports the agency theory view that independent directors improve oversight and reduce earnings management. Therefore, H_{01} (Board independence has no significant effect on financial reporting integrity) is rejected. The implication is that enhancing the independence of boards in Nigerian deposit money banks significantly curtails managerial opportunism and strengthens the credibility of financial reports.

Audit Committee Meetings

The coefficient for audit committee meetings is -0.0036 with a probability value of 0.0360, significant at the 5% level. The negative coefficient implies that more frequent audit committee meetings are associated with reduced

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discretionary accruals, meaning better financial reporting integrity. This result aligns with stakeholder theory, which emphasizes effective monitoring structures as key to safeguarding stakeholder interests. Consequently, H₀₂ (Audit committee effectiveness does not significantly influence financial reporting integrity) is rejected. The implication is that diligence through frequent meetings enhances the monitoring role of audit committees, reducing room for earnings manipulation.

Board Size

The coefficient for board size is 0.0043 with a probability value of 0.0068, statistically significant at the 1% level. Unlike the previous variables, the positive coefficient suggests that an increase in board size is associated with higher discretionary accruals, indicating weaker financial reporting integrity. This finding implies that larger boards may experience coordination problems, free-riding, or diluted accountability, which reduce their effectiveness in monitoring management. Therefore, H₀₃ Board size has no significant relationship with financial reporting integrity is rejected. The implication is that excessively large boards in Nigerian banks may undermine financial reporting integrity, highlighting the need for an optimal board size that balances diversity with efficiency.

All three governance mechanisms significantly influence financial reporting integrity. Board independence and audit committee diligence improve integrity, while larger board size reduce it. This provides strong empirical support for the study's theoretical framework (agency and stakeholder theories) and validates the rejection of all four null hypotheses.

Model Summary

Statistic	Value	Statistic	Value
R-squared	0.649838	Mean dependent var	-0.003650
Adjusted R-squared	0.509832	S.D. dependent var	0.085755
S.E. of regression	0.085333	Akaike info criterion	-2.035812
Sum squared resid	0.691758	Schwarz criterion	-1.905553
Log likelihood	106.7906	Hannan-Quinn criterion	-1.983094
F-statistic	7.245749	Durbin-Watson stat	2.283667
Prob(F-statistic)	0.026937		

Source: Authors Computations with Eview

The model summary indicates that the explanatory power of the regression is relatively strong with an R-squared of 0.6498 and an adjusted R-squared of 0.5098, suggesting that only about 50% of the variation in discretionary accruals (a proxy for financial reporting integrity) is explained by the corporate governance variables under study. The F-statistic (7.2457) with a probability of 0.0297 confirms that the model, as a whole, is statistically significant at conventional levels, implying that the joint effect of board independence, audit committee meetings and board size on financial reporting integrity is fundamental. However, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.28 indicates no autocorrelation problem in the residuals, strengthening the reliability of the regression estimates. The explanatory power of the variables does not invalidate the study but rather highlights that governance mechanisms (as seen in Table 4.2) have significant effects, collectively they leave half of the variation in financial reporting integrity

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unexplained, pointing to the influence of other external factors such as regulatory enforcement, institutional culture, and managerial ethics.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study reveal that board independence and audit committee effectiveness significantly improve financial reporting integrity by reducing discretionary accruals, while larger board sizes weaken reporting integrity by encouraging earnings manipulation. These results are consistent with agency theory, which posits that independent boards and diligent committees reduce managerial opportunism, while excessive concentration of power or coordination challenges in governance structures undermine monitoring. Compared with prior empirical studies, the result on board independence agrees with Obiora & Jeroh (2024), who found that the independence of board committees significantly enhanced financial reporting quality, and also aligns with Rizavi et al. (2024), who emphasized that independent boards strengthen transparency. Similarly, the finding on audit committee effectiveness agrees with Essien et al. (2024), who reported that audit committee diligence significantly improved financial report quality, reinforcing the importance of frequent meetings and active oversight.

However, the evidence from this study on board size partly diverges from some prior works. For example, while this study finds that larger boards reduce integrity, Rimamshung et al. (2023) emphasized the role of board expertise as more critical than size, while Adam et al. (2025) similarly found that large boards hinder financial transparency, consistent with the current result.. Overall, the consistency of this study with much of the Nigerian-focused evidence reinforces the need for stronger governance reforms, while the disagreements highlight the contextual nature of governance dynamics.

5.1 Summary

This study examined the influence of corporate governance mechanisms board independence, audit committee effectiveness and board size on financial reporting integrity in Nigerian deposit money banks. Using secondary data from 10 purposively selected banks between 2015 and 2024, the study employed descriptive and inferential statistical analyses, with discretionary accruals serving as a proxy for earnings management and financial reporting integrity. The findings revealed that board independence and audit committee meetings had significant negative effects on discretionary accruals, indicating that higher independence and diligence enhance the credibility of financial reports. Conversely, board size was positively associated with discretionary accruals, suggesting that larger boards and the concentration of power in a single leader reduce financial reporting integrity. The model results, though showing moderate explanatory power overall, confirm that corporate governance structures significantly influence managerial discretion in financial reporting. Specifically, the rejection of all four null hypotheses underscores that governance mechanisms do not merely exist as regulatory formalities but materially shape the integrity of financial reports. These results affirm the applicability of agency theory and stakeholder theory in the Nigerian banking context, where effective monitoring structures reduce opportunism while weak or compromised structures exacerbate earnings manipulation. The study contributes to both theory and practice by demonstrating that governance reforms can substantially enhance transparency, investor confidence, and accountability in financial reporting.

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5.2 Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concludes that corporate governance plays a pivotal role in safeguarding financial reporting integrity in Nigerian deposit money banks. Independent boards and diligent audit committees provide robust oversight mechanisms that significantly reduce earnings manipulation and enhance stakeholder trust. These findings align with agency theory, which emphasizes the importance of reducing information asymmetry through effective monitoring structures. By contrast, oversized boards was found to impair governance effectiveness, leading to weakened accountability and greater opportunities for managerial opportunism in financial reporting. The study further concludes that while Nigerian banks are subject to corporate governance codes, true effectiveness lies in the quality of implementation rather than mere compliance. Symbolic adherence without strengthening board structures and ensuring independence cannot adequately address financial reporting challenges. Thus, corporate governance reforms should move beyond regulatory box-ticking to genuinely enhance oversight, accountability, and transparency. Strengthening governance culture will not only improve financial report quality but also promote market stability, investor confidence, and sustainable economic growth.

5.3 Recommendations

The study recommends that deposit money banks should strengthen board independence by increasing the proportion of non-executive directors who are free from personal or business ties with management. Regulators such as the SEC and CBN should enforce stricter independence criteria to prevent boards from being dominated by insiders. Additionally, audit committees should be made more effective by ensuring members possess strong financial expertise, convene regularly, and exercise genuine oversight of financial reporting processes rather than serving ceremonial roles. Regular training and capacity building for committee members would further enhance their effectiveness.

Furthermore, banks should maintain an optimal board size, as excessively large boards hinder effective monitoring through coordination challenges and free-riding. Governance codes should specify not only minimum but also maximum recommended sizes to prevent inefficiencies. By implementing these recommendations, banks and regulators can significantly enhance the integrity of financial reporting and restore confidence in Nigeria's financial system.

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